

Return On Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Return On Investment (ROI) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the ROI ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the ROI ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the ROI ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 274 journal publications regarding the ROI ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the ROI ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 85 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 28 topics around the influence of the ROI ratio and 38 topics about the determinants of the ROI ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around ROI ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Return on Investment (ROI); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking.

Introduction

In the banking industry, Return On Investment (ROI) generally used to measure how effective a bank is in generating profits from investments made in financial instruments or funds provided to customers in the form of credit. ROI provides an idea of how much profit is generated from each fund invested by the bank, and how effective the bank is in utilizing the funds it has. The use of ROI in the banking industry is nothing new. ROI has been used as an important financial performance indicator for the past few decades. However, along with the development of technology and the banking business, the use of ROI continues to grow and is integrated with other financial analysis methods to provide a more complete picture of a bank's financial performance.

Apart from being an indicator of bank financial performance, ROI is also used as an evaluation tool for investors. A high ROI shows that the bank is effective in generating profits from the investments made, thereby attracting investors to invest in the bank. However, the use of ROI also has limitations. ROI only measures profits relative to investment, and does not provide an idea of the true magnitude of profits. ROI can also be affected by other factors such as risk and return on investment. To overcome these limitations, ROI is often integrated with other financial analysis methods such as other financial ratio analysis and qualitative analysis. Qualitative analysis involves evaluating non-financial aspects that influence bank financial performance such as risk management and service quality. In this way, ROI can provide a more complete picture of a bank's financial performance.

ROI in banking is a fairly broad research topic and continues to grow along with developments in technology and the banking business. The following are some of the latest developments in research regarding ROI in banking: first, research

shows that ROI can be used as a better indicator of financial performance than traditional financial ratios such as Return on Equity (ROE). ROI provides a more accurate picture of how effective the bank is in generating profits from the investments made. Second, research also shows that ROI can be used to evaluate financing credit provided by banks to customers. ROI can help banks to decide whether investment in certain financing credits will produce adequate profits. Third, ROI can also be used to measure the effectiveness of risk management in banking. ROI can help banks to identify the risks that must be taken in investments, and ensure that these investments generate adequate profits. Fourth, research also shows that ROI can be used to evaluate technology investments in banking. ROI can help banks to decide whether certain technology investments will generate adequate profits and help banks increase efficiency and productivity. Fifth, research also shows that ROI can be used as a tool to measure banking financial performance in the context of sustainable banking. ROI can help banks to ensure that investments made not only generate adequate profits, but also have a positive impact on society and the environment. Overall, research on ROI in banking continues to develop and is used in various contexts to help banks increase operational effectiveness and efficiency and provide a positive impact on society and the environment.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around ROI in Islamic and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics around ROI. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research ROI. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the ROI ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Return on Investment (ROI) in banking refers to the ratio of profits to investments made by the bank. ROI can be calculated by dividing the bank's net profit by the total investment made. In banking, investment usually refers to capital invested by bank owners or other investors, as well as funds obtained from customers that are deposited or loaned by the bank. Meanwhile, net profit is the difference between income and costs incurred by the bank during a certain period. For example, if a bank earns a net profit of 1 billion rupiah this year and the total investment is 10 billion rupiah, then the ROI is 10%. This means the bank makes 10 cents for every dollar invested. ROI is one way to measure a bank's efficiency and success in managing investments. The higher the ROI, the better the bank's performance in generating profits from the investments made. However, keep in mind that ROI only provides a limited picture and cannot be used as the only indicator of bank performance.

Bibliometric studies are research methods that use quantitative analysis to measure and analyze literature production in a field or scientific discipline. This method is often used to evaluate the academic performance of authors, journals, institutions or even countries in certain fields of science. Bibliometric studies collect and analyze bibliographic data from documents related to a specific topic, such as journal articles, books, conferences, theses, and research reports. This bibliographic data is then used to produce metrics that describe the productivity and influence of an author, journal, or institution in the field. Metrics often used in bibliometric studies are number of publications, citation frequency, Hirsch index (H-index), and citation ratio. Bibliometric studies can provide insight into research trends in a field,

as well as assist researchers, publishers, and policy makers in making decisions. However, it should be remembered that bibliometric studies have limitations, such as the inability to measure the quality or relevance of scientific work, as well as the tendency to ignore less popular or less published scientific disciplines.

VOSviewer is free software for analysis and visualization of bibliometric data. This software was developed by researchers from Leiden University in the Netherlands and can be used to visualize patterns of relationships between publications, authors, journals and keywords in a particular field. VOSviewer uses bibliographic data that has been taken from sources such as research databases or Google Scholar. This data is then analyzed using an algorithm to identify patterns that show relationships between publications, authors, journals and keywords. The results of this analysis can be visualized in the form of 2D or 3D graphics, including network maps, citation maps, and cluster trees. VOSviewer can be used for various purposes, such as to assist in selecting journals for publication, evaluating relationships between concepts in a scientific field, and understanding trends in research or publications. VOSviewer can also help researchers identify leading researchers in a particular field, as well as gain a better understanding of collaboration between researchers and institutions. VOSviewer is popular software among researchers, publishers, and policy makers interested in the analysis and visualization of bibliometric data.

Library Research study is a research method carried out by investigating, collecting and evaluating literature or other sources of information related to a particular research topic or problem. The purpose of a Library Research study is to compile or summarize existing knowledge about a particular topic and gain a better understanding of research trends, leaps in knowledge that have occurred, and gaps that still exist in the research. Library Research studies can be carried out in various scientific disciplines, such as social sciences, health, technology and natural sciences. This method involves collecting and reviewing literature from various sources, such as journals, books, research reports, official documents, and trusted websites. The Library Research study process includes several steps, including determining research questions, selecting relevant keywords, finding and selecting relevant literature sources, evaluating the quality of the literature sources found, and making a synthesis or analysis of the literature sources.. Library Research studies can provide benefits in various fields, such as in developing policies, producing research reports, developing theories, or in strengthening the knowledge base needed to conduct further research. Therefore, the ability to carry out Library Research studies well is an important ability possessed by a researcher.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Return on Investment (ROI). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on ROI in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Return on Investment " and " ROI " over the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around ROI using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on year of publication; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around ROI using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items ; and (3) mapping research topics around ROI using a Library Research study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Return on Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 274 Sinta accredited national journal based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2003 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding ROI by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2003	1	2012	6	2018	26
2007	1	2013	18	2019	24
2008	2	2014	17	2020	32
2009	2	2015	16	2021	41
2010	4	2016	6	2022	50
2011	3	2017	19	2023	6

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Study Mapping Research Regarding Return on Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Article search results in Perish/Harzing software are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

to its own capital (equity). The influence of ROI on DER in banking can vary depending on the situation and conditions of the banking itself. In general, the higher a banking ROI, the less need it needs to use debt to finance its operations. This is because a high ROI shows that banks are able to generate sufficient income to finance their operational activities and generate sufficient profits to meet capital requirements. On the other hand, if banking ROI is low, then banks may need to consider using more debt to finance their operations. This is because banks may not be able to generate sufficient income to finance their operational activities and pay interest on debt. However, although ROI and DER can influence each other, they do not always correlate with each other. There are banking companies that are able to generate high ROI even though they use high DER, and vice versa. In this case, it is important for banking management to consider various factors that influence ROI and DER, such as market conditions, capital requirements, credit risk, and other factors in making appropriate financial decisions.

(2) Dividend Payout Ratio /DPR. The influence of ROI on DPR in banking is closely related to the dividend policy implemented by the bank. If banking ROI increases, then the bank tends to have more profits that can be distributed to shareholders. This will allow banks to increase the DPR or the amount of dividends paid to shareholders. However, the decision to increase DPR does not only depend on ROI alone. There are several other factors that must be considered, such as banking policies, capital requirements, cash flow, economic conditions, and applicable regulatory requirements. In the banking industry, DPR usually tends to be more stable compared to other companies because banks are often regulated by strict regulations regarding dividend payments. For example, banks may be required to maintain certain levels of reserves to anticipate risks that may arise in the future. In this case, the influence of ROI on DPR in banking must be considered carefully and must be adjusted to various other factors that influence banking dividend policy.

(3) Share prices. The influence of ROI on share prices in banking can be influenced by several factors, including: first, the company 's financial performance. _ A high ROI indicates that a company can generate greater profits with fewer assets, thereby indicating good financial performance. This can increase investor confidence and encourage demand for shares, thereby increasing share prices. second, interest rate level. _ _ _ ROI in banking is influenced by interest rates, because banks earn income from interest received from providing credit. If interest rates fall, ROI may also fall, which can affect stock prices. Third, competition in the industry. The high level of competition in the banking industry can affect ROI and share prices. Intense competition can lead to low ROI and depress stock prices. Fourth, regulation. _ Government regulations can affect ROI and share prices in banking. Strict regulations can limit banking revenues and impact ROI, which in turn can affect share prices. In general, a high ROI can have a positive impact on banking share prices. However, other factors such as interest rates, competition, and regulation may also influence this relationship. Therefore, investors must consider all these factors when analyzing investments in banking.

(4) Foreign direct investment. Return on Investment (ROI) can influence foreign direct investment in banking. ROI is the ratio of the net profit obtained from an investment compared to the cost of the investment itself. If the ROI of a banking company is high, it will show that the investment produces profits that are greater than the costs incurred, and this will increase foreign investors' confidence in investing in banking. Foreign direct investment in banking can bring major benefits to the country, such as bringing new technology and expertise, increasing the workforce, and increasing exports. However, to attract foreign direct investment, the ROI must be attractive enough to guarantee the investor a profit.

(5) Social investment in implementing Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR. Social investment and CSR are company actions to make positive contributions to

society and the surrounding environment, in addition to financial profits. ROI on social and CSR investments in banking is difficult to measure directly, because the results of social and CSR investments are not always in the form of immediately visible financial benefits. However, ROI can still influence social and CSR investments in banking indirectly. In the long term, social investment and CSR can help banks strengthen their reputation and increase customer and investor confidence. This can help banks expand market share and increase profits in the long term.

(6) Infrastructure investment. The effect of ROI on infrastructure investment in banking is as follows: first, investment decisions. ROI is often the main factor considered by banks when deciding to invest in infrastructure. The higher the expected ROI, the more likely banks are to allocate resources to the investment. Second, business growth. Successful infrastructure investments can strengthen the foundation of a banking business and enable banks to offer new products and services, increase competitive advantage, and grow market share. Third, operational efficiency. Appropriate infrastructure investment can increase bank operational efficiency, reduce operational costs and risks, and increase productivity and performance.

(7) Investor welfare. The effect of ROI on infrastructure investment in banking is as follows: first, investment decisions. ROI is often the main factor considered by banks when deciding to invest in infrastructure. The higher the expected ROI, the more likely banks are to allocate resources to the investment. Second, business growth. Successful infrastructure investments can strengthen the foundation of a banking business and enable banks to offer new products and services, increase competitive advantages, and grow market share. Third, operational efficiency. Appropriate infrastructure investment can increase bank operational efficiency, reduce operational costs and risks, and increase productivity and performance.

(8) Investor satisfaction. A high ROI tends to increase investor satisfaction because it shows that the company can generate good returns from their investment. This can strengthen investors' confidence in the company and encourage them to maintain or even increase their investment in the company.

(9) Dividend policy. A high ROI tends to increase investor satisfaction because it shows that the company can generate good returns from their investment. This can strengthen investors' confidence in the company and encourage them to maintain or even increase their investment in the company.

(10) Economic benefits with socio-cultural values. High ROI can make a significant contribution to economic profits with socio-cultural value. By generating high profits, companies can expand their business and create new jobs. This can help improve economic prosperity in the regions where the company operates.

(11) Financial performance. ROI can significantly influence banking financial performance. The higher the ROI, the greater the profit a company makes from their investment. This can increase net profit margins, strengthen the capital base, and increase the efficiency of using company resources.

(12) Company performance. ROI can help banking companies in mitigating information security risks. Investments in effective security systems and IT infrastructure can help companies protect information assets and reduce security risks. This can help protect customer personal information and maintain the company's reputation.

(13) Information security risk mitigation. ROI can help banking companies in mitigating information security risks. Investments in effective security systems and IT infrastructure can help companies protect information assets and reduce security risks. This can help protect customer personal information and maintain the company's reputation.

(14) Working capital. A high ROI can increase a company's working capital,

because the company can use profits from investments to fund operational activities and obtain additional funds from investors who are interested in a good ROI. On the other hand, low ROI can affect a company's working capital because banking companies may have difficulty getting the funding needed to run their operations.

(15) Company value. A high ROI can increase a company's working capital, because the company can use profits from investments to fund operational activities and obtain additional funds from investors who are interested in a good ROI. On the other hand, low ROI can affect a company's working capital because banking companies may have difficulty getting the funding needed to run their operations.

(16) Use of working capital. High ROI can affect the company's use of working capital. With a high ROI, a company can use profits to improve its use of working capital and expand its operations. Conversely, a low ROI can reduce a company's use of working capital because banking companies may have difficulty obtaining the funding needed to run their operations.

(17) Profit growth. A high ROI shows that the investment made by the company has succeeded in generating greater profits. In this case, high ROI can encourage company profit growth. For example, if a banking company invests funds in sectors that produce high ROI, such as providing credit with higher interest, then the profits generated will increase significantly. However, keep in mind that ROI does not guarantee stable profit growth in the long term. Therefore, banking companies must manage investment risks carefully to ensure sustainable profit growth.

(18) Distribution of Ziswaf funds (Zakat, Infaq, alms and Waqf). In Islam, zakat, infaq, alms and waqf are obligations for Muslims who can afford it. Sharia banking has the responsibility to manage Ziswaf funds from customers and channel them to sectors that comply with sharia principles. ROI can be an indicator for sharia banking to determine projects that are worthy of receiving Ziswaf funds. Projects that have a high ROI can provide greater profits and help sharia banks to fulfill their obligations in distributing Ziswaf funds.

(19) Prediction of company bankruptcy. ROI can be an important financial performance indicator in predicting the possibility of company bankruptcy. A low ROI can indicate that the investments made by the company are ineffective and do not generate sufficient profits to meet the company's financial obligations. In this case, ROI can be a signal for company management to make changes to investment strategy or financial restructuring to avoid the possibility of company bankruptcy. However, ROI should not be the only indicator in predicting company bankruptcy. There are other factors to consider, such as market conditions, competition, and overall economic conditions.

(20) Price to Book Value /PBV. Basically, the higher the ROI, the better the company's performance in generating profits from the investments made. This will affect PBV, where the higher the ROI, the higher the PBV value. Conversely, if ROI is low, PBV will tend to be lower. In the banking industry, ROI is usually strongly influenced by loan performance and effective asset management. When bank loans are managed well and bank assets are managed effectively, ROI can increase and PBV can also increase.

(21) Return On Assets /ROA. ROI measures the rate of return on investments made, while ROA measures the efficiency of using assets to generate profits. In the banking context, ROI and ROA have a close relationship and influence each other. ROI can influence ROA in two ways: first, a high ROI can increase ROA: If the bank is able to generate high returns on investment, it will increase the profits obtained from the assets owned. This will increase ROA. Second, low ROI can reduce ROA: If the bank is unable to generate good returns on investment, then the profits generated from the assets owned will be lower. This will reduce ROA.

(22) Return On Equity /ROE. In the banking context, ROI and ROE have an interrelated influence. The higher a company's ROI, the more likely it is that ROE

will increase. This is because ROI measures the rate of return on all capital used, while ROE only measures the return on shareholder capital. In practice, high ROI and ROE usually indicate a company that is financially healthy and performing well. However, a high ROI can occur due to the use of high debt or greater risk, which can lower the ROE. Conversely, a high ROE may occur due to a healthy capital structure, but the ROI may not always be high. Therefore, while ROI and ROE have interrelated influences, they need to be assessed simultaneously to understand the overall financial health of a banking company.

(23) Stock returns. High ROI tends to increase banking profits, which can increase share prices. Conversely, a low ROI can lower stock prices because investors tend to expect greater returns on their investments.

(24) Systematic risk. ROI can help banks manage systematic risks, namely risks that are related to overall economic conditions and cannot be controlled by the bank directly. A high ROI can help banks reduce systematic risk because the bank will be better able to survive difficult times.

(25) Tourism sector. The impact of ROI on the tourism sector on banking may not be immediately visible, but a high ROI can enable banks to provide more loans to tourism businesses and support the growth of this sector.

(26) Capital structure. A high ROI can increase a bank's ability to obtain capital through issuing shares or bonds because investors will be more interested in investing in banks that have a good ROI. Conversely, a low ROI can affect a bank's capital structure because it will be difficult for the bank to obtain new capital.

(27) Economic rate of return. High ROI can contribute to economic growth because banks will provide more loans to projects that have the potential to produce high ROI. This will increase the overall rate of return for the economy.

(28) Promotion success rate. ROI can also influence the success of bank promotions. A high ROI can be used as evidence that the bank is able to provide good profits for investors, so that it can help in the bank's promotional efforts. Conversely, a low ROI can complicate a bank's promotional efforts because investors will be more likely to choose another bank that has a higher ROI.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinant Variables of Return on Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 38 ROI determinant variables in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Acquisition. Acquisitions can have a positive impact on banking ROI if the acquired company has quality assets or has a growing market. However, acquisitions can also have a negative impact on ROI if the acquired company has high debt or does not have good growth.

(2) Cash Turnover. Cash turnover can have a positive impact on banking ROI because the higher the cash turnover rate, the more efficient the use of cash in bank operations. However, keep in mind that a higher cash turnover rate can also indicate higher credit risk.

(3) Capital Expenditure. High capital expenditure (CAPEX) in banking can reduce ROI in the short term due to high investment costs, but can increase ROI in the long term if the investment is successful in increasing revenue or operational efficiency.

(4) Current Ratio. The current ratio can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows the bank's ability to meet short-term obligations smoothly. A high current ratio can indicate that the bank has good liquidity and is not too dependent on short-term debt.

(5) Debt to Equity Ratio /DER. DER can have a negative impact on banking ROI if it is too high because it shows that the bank relies on debt funding. This can increase financial risk and limit the bank's ability to generate profits.

(6) Debt to Total Assets /DTA. DTA can have a negative impact on banking ROI if it is too high because it indicates that the bank has too much debt to pay off. This can increase financial risk and limit the bank's ability to generate profits.

(7) Degree of Financial Leverage /DFL. The impact of DFL on ROI in banking can be complex and vary depending on many factors such as bank capital structure, business risk, interest rates, and market conditions. In general, a high DFL can cause large ROI fluctuations, especially in volatile interest rate conditions. High DFL can also make banks more vulnerable to financial risk.

(8) Business ethics (placement in the right position, managing organizational resources well, utilizing power appropriately, trying to act fairly, being responsible for the company's image). Business ethics can have a positive impact on banking ROI because ethical behavior can increase the bank's reputation and the trust of customers. In the long term, a good reputation can increase customer trust and generate greater returns.

(9) Equity to Total Assets Ratio. Equity to total assets ratio can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows how large a share of bank assets is funded with equity. The higher this ratio, the fewer bank liabilities are funded by debt, and the greater the customer's trust in the bank.

(10) Fixed Asset Turnover /FATO. FATO can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows efficiency in the use of bank fixed assets to generate income. The higher the FATO, the better the bank utilizes its fixed assets and the higher the probability of generating greater returns.

(11) Gross Profit Margin /GPM. GPM can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows the bank's efficiency in generating profits from sales of products and services. The higher the GPM, the more likely the bank is to generate greater returns.

(12) Inventory Turnover Ratio /ITR. ITR can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows the bank's efficiency in managing product inventory. The higher the Inventory Turnover Ratio, the more efficient the bank is in utilizing its product inventory, which can increase profits and returns.

(13) Initial Public Offering /IPO. An IPO can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it allows banks to obtain significant funds from the capital markets to fund business expansion or pay down debt. This can increase profits and generate greater returns for shareholders.

(14) Working capital policy. Working capital policy can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows how well the bank manages cash flow and inventory to maximize returns. By using a good working capital policy, banks can obtain sufficient funds to finance their operational activities and increase efficiency, which can increase returns.

(15) Problem/bad credit. Problematic/bad credit can have a negative impact on banking ROI because it can cause losses and additional costs. If a bank experiences problematic/non-performing loans, the bank must prepare sufficient reserves to cover expected losses, which can reduce returns.

(16) Liquidity. Liquidity can have a positive impact on banking ROI because it shows the bank's ability to meet its short-term financial obligations and provide services to customers. The more liquid a bank is, the less risk it has of failing to meet its short-term financial obligations, which can increase customer confidence and increase returns.

(17) Mergers. Mergers can have a positive or negative impact on banking ROI, depending on how well the merger is executed. A well-executed merger can increase cost savings and increase efficiency, which can increase returns. However, a bad merger can cause additional costs and losses that can lower returns.

(18) Foreign capital. Foreign capital can have a positive impact on banking ROI as it can provide access to global markets and additional financial resources.

Foreign capital can also improve efficiency and expand geographic reach, which can increase returns. However, foreign capital can also carry foreign exchange risks and unstable government policies, which can lower returns.

(19) Working capital. Working capital policies can have a positive impact on banking ROI because they can increase efficiency and optimize resource use. By using a good working capital policy, banks can obtain sufficient funds to finance their operational activities and increase efficiency, which can increase returns.

(20) Net Interest Margin /NIM. The influence of NIM on ROI in banking is quite significant. A high NIM can increase ROI, because the greater the NIM, the greater the interest income received by the bank from lending and investment activities. In addition, banks with high NIMs can also generate more profits from non-interest income sources such as administration fees and commissions.

(21) Net Profit Margin /NPM. In banking, high NPM can have a positive impact on ROI. Banks that have a high NPM tend to be able to generate more net profits from their operations, including from the products and services provided. These profits can then be used to strengthen the bank's capital and expand its business, thereby increasing the bank's ROI.

(22) Mudharabah Financing. Mudharabah financing can affect ROI in banking because this financing is directly related to business activities and generates profits. When Islamic banks provide Mudharabah financing to businesses, they will get a share of the profits from the business as investors. If the business is successful and produces large profits, investors will gain significant profits.

(23) Fixed asset turnover. Fixed Asset Turnover can influence ROI in banking because it measures how efficiently the bank uses its fixed assets to generate income. The higher the fixed asset turnover, the more efficient the bank is in utilizing its fixed assets to generate income. This can increase ROI in banking.

(24) Receivables turnover. In this case, faster receivables turnover can increase ROI because banks can use funds collected from receivables for investment in a faster time. The faster the turnover of receivables, the higher the ROI the bank can achieve.

(25) Inventory turnover. If inventory turnover increases, banks can optimize income from investments and allocate funds more effectively. This can positively influence banking ROI. However, if inventory turnover is too low, banks may face liquidity risks and lower investment returns, which can negatively affect banking ROI.

(26) Quick Ratio. If the Quick Ratio is high, it means the bank has a better ability to pay short-term obligations, and can provide confidence to investors and creditors. This can positively influence banking ROI. On the other hand, if the Quick Ratio is low, the bank can face financial risks and can negatively affect banking ROI.

(27) Current asset turnover ratio. The current asset turnover ratio measures the bank's ability to generate income from the current assets it owns. The higher the current asset turnover ratio, the more efficient the bank is in using current assets to generate income. In this case, the bank will have more revenue that can be used to generate profits and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the current asset turnover ratio, the better the effect on banking ROI.

(28) Working capital turnover ratio. The working capital turnover ratio measures a bank's efficiency in managing its working capital. The higher the working capital turnover ratio, the more efficient the bank is in managing and utilizing its working capital. In this case, the bank will be more efficient in managing its finances and assets, so that it can generate more income and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the working capital turnover ratio, the better the impact on banking ROI.

(29) Cash turnover ratio. The cash turnover ratio measures a bank's ability to generate income from the cash it has. The higher the cash turnover ratio, the more efficient the bank is in using its cash to generate income. In this case, the bank will

have more revenue that can be used to generate profits and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the cash turnover ratio, the better the impact on banking ROI.

(30) Receivable Turnover. Receivable turnover measures a bank's efficiency in collecting bills from its customers. The higher the receivable turnover, the faster the bank will collect bills from its customers. In this case, the bank will be more efficient in managing its receivables and increase its liquidity. With better liquidity, banks can use available funds to generate higher revenues and increase their ROI. Therefore, the higher the receivable turnover, the better the impact on banking ROI.

(31) Sales Growth. Sales growth measures the growth of bank revenue from year to year. The higher the sales growth, the more income the bank generates. In this case, the bank can use the revenue generated to generate profits and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the sales growth, the better the impact on banking ROI.

(32) Internal Control System (application of authority and responsibility, transaction recording, physical control, appropriate accounting system, monitoring and evaluation). The internal control system is the process a bank uses to control risks and maintain the integrity of its operations. In this case, an internal control system can help banks avoid losing money, protect customer interests, and reduce the risk of errors and fraud. By having a strong internal control system, banks can increase their efficiency and reduce unnecessary operational costs. This can increase a bank's profitability and, thereby, increase its ROI. Therefore, the stronger the internal control system, the better its impact on banking ROI.

(33) Company size. Company size can affect ROI in banking. The larger the company, the more resources and markets are available for the bank to generate revenue and increase its ROI. However, the bigger the company, the more complex and difficult it is to manage. Therefore, company size can have a positive or negative influence on ROI, depending on how effectively the bank manages its operations and resources.

(34) Long-term debt. Long-term debt measures the amount of loans received by banks with a term of more than one year. The higher the long-term debt, the more interest the bank will have to pay each year, which can affect its net profit and ROI. However, long-term debt can benefit a bank by providing an additional source of funding that can be used to generate revenue and increase its ROI. Therefore, the impact of long-term debt on ROI depends on how effective the bank is in managing loans and is able to generate higher income from interest costs.

(35) Turnover rate of working capital elements. The turnover rate of working capital elements measures how quickly a bank can generate income from its operational assets. The higher the turnover rate of working capital elements, the more efficient the bank is in managing its operational assets and generating income. In this case, the bank will have more revenue that can be used to generate profits and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the turnover rate of working capital elements, the better the impact on banking ROI.

(36) Total fixed assets. Total fixed assets measure the number of assets used by the bank to carry out its operations, such as buildings, machinery and equipment. The higher the total fixed assets, the more investment required by the bank to operate its business, which can affect its net profit and ROI. However, total fixed assets can also provide benefits for banks by providing stable assets that can be used to generate long-term income. Therefore, the effect of total fixed assets on ROI depends on how effectively the bank manages its fixed assets and is able to generate higher income than operational costs.

(37) Total Assets Turnover /TATO. TATO measures how efficient a bank is in generating income from all its assets, including fixed and current assets. The higher the total assets turnover, the more efficient the bank is in generating income and increasing its ROI. In this case, the bank will have more revenue that can be used to generate profits and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the total assets turnover,

the better the effect on banking ROI.

(38) Working Capital Turnover /WCT. WCT measures how quickly a bank can generate income from its working capital, which includes current assets and current liabilities. The higher the WCT, the more efficient the bank is in managing its working capital and generating income. In this case, the bank will have more revenue that can be used to generate profits and increase its ROI. Therefore, the higher the WCT, the better the impact on banking ROI.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Return On Investment (ROI) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2003 to 2023 which came from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 274 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the ROI ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 85 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 28 topics, cluster 2 consists of 26 topics, cluster 3 consists of 21 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 10 topics. Third, based on mapping studies Library Research, there are 28 topics related to the influence of the ROI ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Dividend Payout Ratio /DPR, share prices, foreign direct investment, social investment implementing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), infrastructure investment, investor welfare, investor satisfaction, dividend policy, economic profits with socio-cultural values, financial performance, company performance, information security risk mitigation, working capital, company value, use of working capital, profit growth, distribution of Ziswaf funds (Zakat, Infaq, alms, and Waqf), predictions of company bankruptcy, Price to Book Value (PBV), Return On Assets (ROA), Return On Equity (ROE), stock returns, systematic risk, tourism sector, capital structure, level of economic return, and level of promotional success. And there are 38 topics related to determining the ROI ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: acquisition, Cash Turnover, Capital Expenditure, Current Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Debt to Total Assets (DTA), Degree of Financial Leverage (DFL), business ethics (placement in the right position, managing organizational resources well, utilizing power appropriately, trying to act fairly, being responsible for the company's image), Equity to Total Assets Ratio, Fixed Asset Turnover (FATO), Gross Profit Margin (GPM), Inventory Turnover Ratio (ITR), Initial Public Offering (IPO), working capital policy, non-performing loans, liquidity, mergers, foreign capital, working capital, Net Interest Margin (NIM), Net Profit Margin (NPM), Mudharabah financing, fixed asset turnover, accounts receivable turnover, inventory turnover, Quick Ratio, current asset turnover ratio, working capital turnover ratio, cash turnover ratio, Receivable Turnover, Sales Growth, Internal Control System (application of authority and responsibility, recording transactions, physical control, appropriate accounting systems, monitoring and evaluation), company size, long-term debt, turnover rate of working capital elements, total fixed assets, Total Assets Turnover (TATO), and Working Capital Turnover (WCT).

The next research recommendation is to use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limited data sample in this research and can add a longer time span of research data. so that the following research results can be obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the Library Research The review can be explained in a more complex way.

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